

**PARENT AND CHILD RELATIONSHIP AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS
THAT COME TO THE SURFACE IN THE FAMILY**

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Abstract: This article examines the shortcomings of family circumstances problems. It is known that classical psychoanalysis was the first scientific direction that laid the relationship of parents and children in the center of the personal development of the child. Psychoanalysis has become a defining direction in the development of basic concepts of child development, in which the main role is assigned to the problem of relations between children and parents (E. Erikson, K. Horney and others). The theory of communion has gained the greatest popularity. The child recognizes himself through the mother's attitude to him, and the mother perceives him as the source of his attitude to him. This complex relationship is initially understood as an attitude that gives a sense of safety and security to oneself and close adults. Modern research on this issue has gone from the study of the child's self-awareness to the study of his *hattiharakts*, which is often described in terms of social adaptation and compensation. Communication is no longer regarded as a relationship, but as a strategy of behavior with the fathers.

Keywords: parental relations, upbringing, educational styles, environment, social, antisocial Family, Child Development.

INTRODUCTION: Objectively, a certain educational system is formed in each family, which is not always implemented by its members. Here we mean the more or less purposeful application of teaching methods and methods, taking into account the understanding of educational goals and the formation of its tasks, what is acceptable and unacceptable for a child. Five of the most common tactics of family upbringing

can be distinguished and four types of family relationships corresponding to them, which are the conditions and consequences of their occurrence: command, guardianship, "non-interference", cooperation and parity. Dictation is the systematic suppression of someone's initiative. Dictatorship in the family is manifested in the systematic behavior of some family members (mainly adults), initiative and self-esteem of other family members. Negligence of parents includes authoritarianism, disregard for the child's interests and opinions, oppression, coercion, if the child resists, sometimes emotional or physical violence against him, ridicule, regularly depriving him of the right to vote in solving problems related to him - all this is a guarantee of serious failures in the formation of his personality. Guardianship is a relationship in which parents satisfy all the needs of the child through their work. Guardianship in the family is a system of relations in which parents meet all the needs of the child with their own efforts, protect him from any worries, actions and difficulties. Parents, in fact, prevent their children from seriously preparing for reality outside the home. It is these children who cannot adapt to society. non-interference - this indicates the coexistence of two worlds: "adults" and "children".

It assumes that two worlds: adults and children, can co-exist, and that neither should cross such a defined line. Often this type of relationship is based on the passivity of parents as educators, and sometimes on their emotional coldness, indifference, inability and unwillingness to learn to be parents. Cooperation - interpersonal relations provide an opportunity to mediate in solving common goals and tasks of joint activities. A family in which the leading type of relationship is cooperation, where parents communicate with their children on an equal basis, where everyone can turn to the other for help with their questions or requests, acquires a unique character. , becomes a social group. Parity is an equal "union" relationship based on the mutual interests of all members of the union.

The concept of parental relationship is the most general and refers to the interaction and interdependence of parents and children. The attitude of parents includes 1061 subjectively evaluated, consciously chosen idea of the child, which determines the characteristics of parents' perception, the way of communication with

the child, the nature of the methods of influencing him. As a rule, emotional, cognitive and behavioral components are distinguished in the structure of parental relations. The concepts of parental status and parental attitude are used synonymously with parental attitude, but differ in the level of awareness. The parent's position is consciously accepted, associated with developed views, intentions; the setting is not very clear. The specificity of parental relations lies in the ambivalence and inconsistency of the parent's position towards the child. On the one hand, this is unconditional love and deep connection, and on the other hand, it is an objective evaluation attitude aimed at forming these methods of social behavior. The relationship of parents is characterized by uniqueness and internal dependence, which lies in the maximum seriousness and intensity of these moments. They can be defined as a personal and objective principle in relation to the child.

Family is a special type of community that plays the main, long-term and most important role in the upbringing of a child's personality. Anxious mothers often raise anxious children. Ambitious parents often oppress their children to such an extent that it causes them to develop an inferiority complex. An uncontrollable father, who loses his temper over trivial excitement, often unknowingly inculcates similar behavior in his children, and so on. According to tradition, the main institution of child education is the family. What the child receives in the family during childhood will be preserved throughout his life. It lays the foundation for the child's personality, and when he enters school, he is already more than half formed as a person. It is in the family that the child gets his first life experience, makes his first observations, learns how to behave in different situations. It is very important that what is taught to the child in the family is confirmed with concrete examples, so that he sees that theory does not deviate from practice in adults. The main role in performing the educational function for children is played by the couple - father and mother. In this regard, they talk about a complete and incomplete family in the absence of one of the parents. The stability of the family environment is an important factor for the child's emotional balance and mental health. The breakdown of the family caused by the separation or separation of parents always

causes a deep shock and leaves a strong resentment in the child, which can only be mitigated. This phenomenon is an important social and educational problem.

The relationship between parents and children is influenced by the type of family, the position held by adults, the style of relationships and the role they assign to the child in the family. His personality is formed under the influence of the type of parental relationship. Research by A.N. Leontiev, A.R. Luria, D.B. Elkonin and others. It was shown that the mental development of the child is determined by the features of his emotional connection and cooperation with his parents. The dynamics of family life and the emotional relationship of parents to a child are important for the formation of his personality. At all stages of the child's development in the family, he is constantly influenced by various factors of the family environment, including the family upbringing style. This can have both a healing and destabilizing effect on the family's educational function, which can cause a variety of problems for the family, its members, and the environment.

According to a study conducted by D.V. According to Berko, the methods of upbringing affect the formation of personality, which can be seen in the level of maturity of the person and in the semantic structure of everyday consciousness. Thus, at the level of characteristics, a significant correlation was established between the educational principles of both parents and personality structures responsible for psychological health, emotional state, behavior regulation, and the level of social adjustment. Girls were more sensitive to the aggressive style of maternal leadership. At the level of characteristics, it is characterized by an increase in the level of aggression, which creates the prerequisites for impulsive behavior. At the level of everyday consciousness - when the opposite image of the world appears, when the image of the mother is presented as "good" but disgusting. The father's role played a decisive role in girls' acceptance of self-realization values, female identity and instrumental values that enable them to achieve their goals and protect their interests. Father's directive style has the greatest impact on girls' productive state (increased depression level, lability of emotional states). Girls who negatively evaluate the educational principles of both parents have cognitive complexity, which provides

neurotic protection of the personality. The father's negative attitude leads to the formation of specific protective reactions in girls that make them want to fight.

Before understanding the nature of the impact of parental relationships on a child, consider its importance in life. The family as a specific social community has always excited the minds of philosophers, historians, sociologists, teachers, psychologists. But today there is still no single definition of the concept of "family" in modern science, although attempts were made many centuries ago by great thinkers (Aristotle, Hegel, Kant, Plato, etc.). In the psychological dictionary for parents, we find the following definition of family: "A family is based on marriage or consanguinity, the members of which are connected by a common life, mutual moral responsibility and mutual support." (40) L.D., Stolyarenko, S.I. As Samygin noted, "the family is a way to optimally satisfy the needs of each member for self-preservation (generation) and self-respect (self-esteem). According to researchers dealing with family problems (I.M. Balinsky, A.I. Zakharov, I.A. Sikhorsky, etc.), the family can be a positive or negative factor in child upbringing.

CONCLUSION: Thus, the method and type of upbringing, the nature of the relationship of parents to children changes not only in time, but also in space. So, culturally, the European tradition is that young children need the strictest discipline, and as the child grows up, discipline should become weaker and he should have more independence. At the same time, the Japanese provide babies with maximum freedom, almost do not restrict them. Discipline, very strict, here, unlike the European tradition, appears during the growth of the child, who later learns the norms and behavior of adults. The style and type of education depends not only on socio-cultural rules and norms presented in the form of educational traditions, but also on the pedagogical position of parents on how to build relationships between children and parents in the family, what qualities and characteristics are formed in children. . Accordingly, the parent determines the model of the child's behavior. Many psychologists of different schools and areas have focused on the importance of the relationship between parents and children. Relationships with close adults play a crucial role in a child's development.

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